

Review Article

Chikungunya in Children

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Abstract:

Chikungunya fever is caused by Chikungunya virus (CHIK) and spread by Aedes aegypti and Aedes albopictus. The median incubation period is 2 to 4 days. Clinical manifestations are very variable, from asymptomatic illness to severe debilitating disease. Common clinical features include abrupt onset of high grade fever, skin rashes, minor hemorrhagic manifestations, arthralgia/arthritis, lymph-adenopathy, conjunctival injection, swelling of eyelids and pharyngitis. Unusual clinical features include seizures, altered level of consciousness, blindness due to retrobulbar neuritis and acute flaccid paralysis. Watery stools may be seen in infants. Treatment is symptomatic. Generally non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs are avoided. Paracetamol may be used for pain and fever. However, NSAIDS may be required for relief of severe arthralgia during convalescent phase.

Key word: Arthritis, Chikungunya, Viral hemorrhagic fever.

Introduction

Chikungunya is a viral disease caused by the alphavirus that is transmitted to humans by bite of infected *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes. The name is derived from the word 'Makonde' meaning "that which bends up" in reference to the stooped posture developed as a result of the arthritic symptoms of the disease.^{1,2} Clinical manifestations of chikungunya-fever are variable ranging from the asymptomatic illness to a severe debilitating disease. Children are among the group at maximum risk for severe manifestations of the disease and some clinical features in this group are distinct from those seen in adults.³

Epidemiology

Historically the disease has been described as early as 18th century by Dr David Blyden, who himself contracted the disease in 1779.⁴ The first detailed description of chikungunya was given by Marion

Robinson⁵ and W.H.R Lumsden⁶ following an outbreak in the Makonde plateau along the border of Tanzania in 1952. Since 2005, Chikungunya has become an emerging public health problem in Southeast Asia, with large numbers of cases reported in Singapore, Malaysia, and Thailand.⁷ *Aedes albopictus* was identified as the vector in the 2006 Chikungunya outbreak in La Reunion (an island in the Indian Ocean). In the past 50 years, Chikungunya has re-emerged several times in both Africa and Asia.⁸ Rapid and local transmission of Chikungunya occurred in the Caribbean and the Americas within 9 months during 2013–2014.⁹ In 2008, the first recognized outbreak of Chikungunya in Bangladesh was identified in the northwest area of the country. Transmission appeared to be geographically limited to two villages bordering India in northwestern Bangladesh.¹⁰ The last outbreak of Chikungunya in Bangladesh occurred in May 2017.¹⁰

Etiology

The Virus: Chikungunya virus (CHIK) is a member of the Alphavirus genus of the family *Togaviridae*.¹¹ It was first isolated in Tanzania by Ross and colleagues.¹¹ The virus has a positive

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sense single stranded RNA genome with 11,438 base pairs.¹² Its phospholipid envelope contains hemagglutinin protein spikes.⁴

The Host: In humans the virus has no age or sex specificities but it has been seen that children, elderly and immune compromised are the most severely affected.¹³

The Vector: The most effective vector for human transmission is *Aedes aegypti*.¹⁴ However, in the 2007 outbreak in Kerala, it was seen that *Aedes albopictus* played a very important role.¹⁵ Recently the possibility of maternal to child transmission in the perinatal period has been explored.¹⁶

Pathogenesis

Detailed studies on the pathogenesis of chikungunya fever are not available. After the bite from an infected mosquito the virus multiplies in lymphoid and myeloid organs and subsequently induces cellular and humoral immunity which leads to manifestations of the disease.¹⁷ Inflammatory damage to the cartilage in the form of necrosis, collagenosis and fibrosis leads to articular symptoms. This is evidenced by biochemical studies showing elevated levels of mucopolysaccharides, hydroxyproline and proline in the urine of chikungunya affected patients.¹⁸

Clinical Features

Common clinical features include abrupt onset of high grade fever, skin rashes, minor hemorrhagic manifestations, arthralgia/arthritis, lymphadenopathy, conjunctival injection, swelling of eyelids and pharyngitis. Unusual clinical features are neurological manifestations including seizures, altered level of consciousness, blindness due to retrobulbar neuritis and acute flaccid paralysis.¹⁹

Fever: Fever is usually of high grade and children may have fever of more than 104⁰ F.²⁰ **Rash:** Towards the end of the febrile phase (3rd to 5th day), most of the patients develop a diffuse, irritating maculopapular rash commonly on the arms, back and shoulders and occasionally over the entire body. This rash usually lasts 48 hours.¹⁹

Arthritis: The joint pain may be severe and can even prevent sleep in the first few days of the illness.¹⁷ Arthralgia and arthritis are uncommon in children but may be quite severe.⁴ Residual arthralgia is far less frequent in children.⁴

Hemorrhagic manifestations: A classic case of chikungunya is thought not to produce hemorrhagic manifestations.²¹

Neurological manifestations: Alpha viruses are known to cause devastating encephalitis. However neurological manifestations are not common with chikungunya.²⁰

Other manifestations: Lymphadenopathy, conjunctival injection, swelling of eyelids and pharyngitis are common. Headache and myalgia are frequent presenting symptoms. Watery stools may be seen in infants.^{4,19,20}

Neonates: Neonates may be affected by vertical transmission from mothers who are struck with the disease in the perinatal period (-4 days to +1 day). The most common symptoms are fever (79%), rash (82%) and peripheral edema (58%).²²

Differentiating dengue and chikungunya fever

In chikungunya infection, fever occurs early in the course of the illness and is of shorter duration than in dengue. Many constitutional symptoms like headache, pharyngitis, rhinitis, vomiting, constipation, diarrhea, abdominal pain and lymphadenopathy occur with similar frequency in the two diseases. A terminal maculopapular rash, conjunctival injection, myalgia and arthralgia or arthritis is seen more often with chikungunya.¹⁹ Serious hemorrhagic manifestations, hepatomegaly and shock are more frequent with dengue.^{23,24}

Diagnostic Criteria for Chikungunya Case definition

Chikungunya Fever should be suspected when a person develops sudden onset of fever, joint manifestations and rash.²⁵

Cases are to be categorized as:

- a) **Possible case:** A patient meeting only clinical criteria.
- b) **Probable case:** a patient meeting both the clinical and epidemiological criteria.
- c) **Confirmed case:** a patient meeting the laboratory criteria, irrespective of the clinical presentation.

Criteria for the Identification of Chikungunya Infection

Clinical criteria

Acute onset of fever $>38.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ with severe arthralgia/ arthritis not explained by other medical conditions.

Epidemiological criteria

Residing or having visited epidemic areas. Having reported transmission within 15 days prior to the onset of symptoms.

Laboratory Criteria: At least one of the following tests in the acute phase: virus isolation by cell culture, presence of viral RNA by real time RT-PCR (within 5 days of onset of illness), presence of viral specific IgM antibody in single serum sample collected within 5 to 28 days of onset fever or four-fold rise of IgG antibody in samples collected at least three weeks apart (1st sample after 7 days).

Treatment and Prevention

Treatment is predominantly supportive and includes bed rest during the febrile period, adequate hydration and antipyretics/analgesics. Salicylates and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) should be avoided as they may precipitate bleeding manifestations. Post illness arthritis may require prolonged treatment with anti-inflammatory agents and graduated physiotherapy.²⁶ Brighton et al have proposed a possible role of chloroquine in chronic arthritic manifestations of the disease.²⁷ Antivirals, antibiotics and corticosteroids also have no role in the management of chikungunya.²⁶ Preventive measures include elimination of breeding places of Aedes mosquito by removal of water containing receptacles, spraying of insecticide and use of larvicide. In hospitals chikungunya affected viremic patients should be nursed in screened wards or under mosquito nets.²⁸

Conclusion

Chikungunya is an emerging infection in Bangladesh and current surveillance and prevention strategies are insufficient to mount an effective public health response. Increasing human resource capacity for diagnostic testing, effective vector control, and reaching people in deprived or inaccessible areas for treatment and management of cases will be critical for future planning and

control of the ongoing chikungunya outbreak in Bangladesh.

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